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FCCIS

Future Circular Collider Innovation Study

Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Research and Innovation Action

MILESTONE REPORT

MINING THE FUTURE® CHALLENGE CALL OPEN

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Abstract:

Application open for submission on Web. Geology data downloadable from Zenodo (Green, open data). Evaluation board of international experts established. GDPR and IP rules available at the call website. Press release issued by CERN and MUL.

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Delivery Slip

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1. COMPETITION OVERVIEW

The Future Circular Collider (FCC) project envisages the construction of a large-scale Research Infrastructure that is based on a new, 100 km long, quasi-circular particle collider. This particle accelerator would be placed in an underground structure that consists of a tunnel, alcoves at regular intervals, large caverns and access shafts. These facilities would be between 150 and 350 metres underground. The construction project would generate about 9 million m³ of excavated materials. A large quantity of these materials is molasse, a heterogeneous, sedimentary rock frequently found in the Geneva basin.

The Mining the Future® Competition (the Competition) has been launched by MUL and CERN to identify credible means for the innovative re-use of the molasse materials that are expected to be encountered during the construction phase, in order to help reduce the amount of excavated materials that will have to be disposed in landfills.

A Judging Panel of internationally renowned experts from subsurface-engineering, excavation materials re-use, and innovation management will judge the Competition over a period of around one and a half years to select the most promising application(s).

The winner(s) of the Competition will be awarded financial assistance for services required to advance the technology readiness level (TRL) of the proposed technologies, in terms of carrying out further needed tests and analysis activities for the proposed re-use approach in laboratories. This procedure aims at bringing the new product, service or process to market.

The submission of applications to the Competition starts on 30 April 2021. The deadline for submission of applications to the Competition is 31 October 2021. The competition is structured in the following phases:

- Phase 1:
 - o Submission of the applications (30.04.21- 31.10.21)
 - o Evaluation phase for the selection of the most promising applications (01.11.21- 31.12.21)
- Phase 2:
 - o Advancement on technology readiness of the selected proposals (from TRL3 to TRL 4)
 - o Evaluation phase (01.01.22- 31.01.22)
 - o Announcement of the Winner(s) of the competition (August 2022)

An award ceremony (October 2022) will close the event.

2. APPLICATION OPEN FOR SUBMISSION

The submission of applications to the Competition starts on 30 April 2021. The deadline for submission of applications to the Competition is 31 October 2021. All the information related to the Competition can be found on the website: cern.ch/miningthefuture:

How to apply?

Applicants can submit one or more applications by **31 October 2021**.

More information about eligibility, evaluation criteria and the contest proceedings is available in the competition guidelines.

Download the competition guidelines

+ Submit your application

**DEADLINE
31.10**

Figure 1- Extract from the competition website

Who can apply?

The Mining the Future competition is open to all persons and organisations eligible to participate in Horizon 2020:

- Individual persons
- Non-profit, academic and higher education organisations
- International European Interest Organisations (IEIOs)
- For-profit organisations, including companies and consortia that have their corporate

Applicants should present a promising and credible solution for the reuse of excavated molasse materials. The proof-of-concept for the technology should already have been demonstrated in laboratory conditions (TRL3). The technology should credibly be on track to be turned into a product, service or industrial process by 2030 (TRL 9).

Figure 2- Extract from the competition website

Mining the Future® – Challenge-based International Innovation Competition

30 April 2021 to 31 October 2021
Europe/Zurich timezone

- Overview
- Competition website
- Participation Guidelines
- Technical Documentation
- Application and participation forms
- Apply now!**
- Contact
- ✉ fccis-mtf-support@cern.ch

Competition timeline

Application	30 April 2021 to 31 October 2021
Evaluation Phase 1	01 November 2021 to 31 December 2021
Evaluation Phase 2	01 January 2022 to 31 July 2022
Announcement of the winner(s)	August 2022
Award ceremony	October 2022

[Data Privacy Protection Policy: OC no.11 - Privacy Notice](#)

Figure 3 – Indico site for application (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/MiningTheFuture>)

3. EVALUATION BOARD

The Competition “Mining the Future®” will be held from April 2021 to August 2022. The Judging Panel is composed of ten international experts from around the globe in the fields of geology, subsurface engineering, materials science, innovation management and environmental management. The members will be active throughout the competition. The first phase lasting from April to October 2021 for submission of proposals followed by a reviewing and pre-selecting period of the proposed technologies based on the submitted documentation. During the second phase that lasts until mid 2022, the judging panel members will identify one or more winners based on interactive Q&A sessions with the submitting teams using videoconferencing technology.

Table 1 Members of the judging panel

Name	Affiliation, Country
Robert GALLER	Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria
Guillaume ATTARD	CEREMA, France
Jacques BURDIN	Jacques BURDIN Ingénieur Conseil, France
Laetitia D’ALOIA SCHWARTZENTRUBER	CETU, France
Herbert EINSTEIN	MIT Boston, Civil and Environmental Engineering, United States
Klaus MARHOLD	Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien, Austria
Manuela ROCCA	TELT, Italy
Severin SEIFERT	Fraunhofer, Germany
Cedric THALMANN	B+ G Betontechnologie + Materialbewirtschaftung AG, Switzerland
Alexander WYSS	SIMATEC Maschinenbau, Switzerland

Figure 4 – Presentation of the jury members on the website

Robert Galler

Robert Galler is Mining Engineer with specialization in Geotechnics and Tunnelling; he graduated at Montanuniversität Leoben (MUL), Austria. In 1997 he obtained a Ph.D. in Tunnelling. From 1997 to 2007 he worked with GEOCONSULT, an international consultant in the field of underground constructions. From 2001 to 2004 he was head of the underground construction division with about 50 employees and as such Project Manager for several underground projects. From end of 2004 until becoming Professor at MUL in November 2006 he was head of GEOCONSULT Innsbruck and as such Project Manager of an international JV working on the design of the Brenner Base Tunnel. He has experience in several national and international research

Figure 5 – Introduction to the Chair of the Jury on the website

4. MARKETING CAMPAIGN

4.1. OBJECTIVES

Together with the website and the application form, a marketing campaign has been launched on 30 April 2021. The goals of the campaign are to attract quality participants to the competition, resulting in several solid proposals, and to raise awareness of the competition and the FCC project as a whole to reach a broader audience. The objectives are to promote the competition and to support the communications for the FCC project.

Figure 6 – Extract from the English version of the video clip

Figure 7 – Extract from the French video clip

4.2. AUDIENCE

The target audiences are:

- Geology experts, Civil Engineers, Tunneling and Construction Industry in Europe and globally
- Innovators, Technology Transfer Officers, Futurists
- Scientists from other fields
- Funding agencies in Europe and from CERN's Member States and Non-Member States
- Science & Technology journalists
- Policy makers, at regional, national, and European level.

4.3. TOOLS AND CHANNELS

The marketing campaign will include weekly social media posts, stakeholder toolkits, promotion through different channels (technical, non-technical magazines).

4.3.1. Website

The central content piece of the campaign is the contest website cern.ch/miningthefuture.

Figure 8 – Welcome page of the competition website

4.3.2. Social media

The following social media will play a key role in the Mining the Future contest:

- Twitter is an interesting platform since it combines a prevalence of professionals, politicians and media representatives with advanced targeting and sponsoring possibilities. Twitter will be the most effective tool in reaching potential applicants and the wider scientific community efficiently.
- Facebook is the platform with the densest penetration across target audiences, demographics and regions. It will be used to reach the broader public, with any submissions generated through this platform considered by-catch.
- LinkedIn: even more so than Twitter, LinkedIn will allow to reach professional and expert audiences that might submit an application.

4.3.3. Press release

It is planned to have two press releases (in French, English, and German) during the campaign:

- At the start of the campaign, a press release aimed at technical media to gather attention for the competition with our primary target audience of potential applicants.
- After the final event, a press release to announce the winners of the competition.